

(Table 1 Contd.)

9.	β -(α)-Naphthyl-amino-2,4,6 T.P.	2	ethanol	above 320	$R_2COCH_2-CH_2$ NH B		
10.	2-(β)-Phenylamino-propionyl benzofuran	1	acetone	184	$R_4COCH_2-CH_2$ Ph-NH		
11.	β -Benzidiny-(<i>p</i>)-phenyl P.	$\frac{1}{2}$	aq. ethanol	147	$R_2COCH_2CH_2$ A-NH		
12.	β -(α)-Naphthyl-amino-(<i>p</i>)-phenyl P.	$1\frac{1}{2}$	acetone	185	$R_2COCH_2CH_2$ B-NH Ph-NH	21.0, 21.0, 21.8, 21.8, 20.8, 20.7.	21.18 mm
13.	3-(β)-Phenylamino propionyl-4-hydroxy-coumarin	1	ethanol	165	$R_2COCH_2CH_2$ B-NH Ph-NH		

D=Dihydroxy, T=Trihydroxy, P=Propiophenone, Ph=Phenyl,

in the region 3300-3350 cm^{-1} is characteristic of $\nu(-NH)$.

The N.M.R. spectrum of the Mannich bases in $CdCl_2$ shows a multiplet from 6.88 δ to 7.48 δ and a sharp singlet at 4.69 δ indicating the presence of the aromatic and methylene protons, respectively. The absorption of amino proton is observed at 3.30 δ .

Screening for Antibacterial Activity :

The compounds 1, 2, 4, 5, 7 and 12 listed in Table 1 were screened for their inhibitory effects against two organisms viz., *Bacillus cereus* (Gram positive) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative) by agar diffusion technique^{1,8} and the results obtained are depicted in Table 1. The concentration of the soln. was 0.5 mg/ml in D.M.F. The bases were found to exhibit activity against *Bacillus cereus* only. Bacterial cultures were maintained at Microbiology Department of Central Pharmaceutical Laboratory, New Rajnagar, Ghaziabad.

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New 5-Arylamino-2[N-(2'-Mercaptoacetylamino-4'-Arylthiazolo)]-Thiadiazoles(III) : as AChE Inhibitors

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THIADIAZOLES are known as potent fungicide¹, insecticide² and bactericide³. 5-Acylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-sulfonamide, an efficient pre- and postemergent herbicide has been reported by Kirkpatrick⁴.

It is well known that sulfur containing compounds affect their toxic action by inhibition of acetylcholinesterase which exhibit physiological significance in the nervous system⁵. Authors, therefore synthesised the title compounds with a view to study their inhibitory properties against cholinesterase.

5-Arylamino-2-mercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles(I) on condensation with 2-chloroacetyl-amino-4-arylthiazoles(II), afforded the 5-arylamino-2[N-(2'-mercaptoacetyl-amino - 4-arylthiazolo)]-thiadiazoles(III) in ethanol solution. These compounds showed strong peaks at 3280 (NH-stretching), 1680 (C=O); 1550 (cyclic C=N); 1340 (pentacyclic ring); 1260 (N-N=C); 830 (disubstituted benzene ring).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The synthesised compounds were satisfactorily characterised by IR, elemental analyses and TLC.

The 5-arylamino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole⁶(I) and 2-amino-4-arylthiazole⁷ have been prepared by known procedures. Chloroacetylation of the latter yielded 2-chloroacetyl-amino-4-aryl-thiazole(II).

5-(4-Ethoxyphenylamino)-2-[N-(2'-mercaptoacetyl-amino-4'-chlorophenylthiazolo)]-thiadiazole(III) :

A mixture of 0.40 g (0.01 mole) sodium hydroxide and 2.53 g (0.01 mole) 5-(4-ethoxyphenylamino)-2-mercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole was heated under reflux for 30 mnts. 2.88 g (0.01 mole) 2-chloroacetyl-amino-4-chlorophenyl thiazole was added to the above solution and refluxed for additional 4 hours. The reaction mixture was poured in ice cold water. The solid mass thus separated was filtered and crystallised from ethylalcohol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—5-ARYLAMINO-2[N-(2'-MERCAPTOACETYLAMINO-4'-ARYLTHIAZOLO)]-THIADIAZOLES(III)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Yield
1.	4-CH ₃	H	229	67
2.	H	H	236	62
3.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	235	60
4.	4-Cl	H	215	65
5.	2-OCH ₃	H	222	55
6.	4-Br	H	234	58
7.	4-CH ₃	Cl	233	60
8.	H	Cl	230	60
9.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	Cl	231	57
10.	4-Cl	Cl	202	62
11.	2-OCH ₃	Cl	228	55
12.	4-Br	Cl	231	57

Determination of Antiacetylcholinesterase activity:

Method of Colowick *et al*⁸ has been employed to determine the enzyme inhibition which is a modification of Hestrin's⁹ procedure. Compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol and were used at a concentration of 3.8×10^{-4} M. A control containing equal volume of propylene glycol was also run in parallel. All the tested compounds showed considerable inhibition. Neostigmine, a potent AChE inhibitor has been used as standard in similar conditions having I₅₀ value 1.96×10^{-7} . I₅₀ value denotes the concentration required for 50% enzyme inhibition.

TABLE 2—ANTIACETYLCHOLINESTERASE ACTIVITY OF 5-ARYLAMINO-2[N-(2'-MERCAPTOACETYLAMINO-4'-ARYLTHIAZOLO)]-THIADIAZOLES(III)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Conc. used	%inhibition	I ₅₀ value
1.	4-CH ₃	H	3.8×10^{-4}	80.13	2.3×10^{-4}
2.	H	H	3.8×10^{-4}	88.08	2.1×10^{-4}
3.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	H	3.8×10^{-4}	40.41	4.7×10^{-4}
4.	2-OCH ₃	H	3.8×10^{-4}	36.44	5.2×10^{-4}
5.	4-CH ₃	Cl	3.8×10^{-4}	40.41	4.7×10^{-4}
6.	4-Cl	Cl	3.8×10^{-4}	99.70	1.9×10^{-4}
7.	4-Br	Cl	3.8×10^{-4}	85.10	2.2×10^{-4}

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**Leucoanthocyanidins from *Saraca asoca*
Stem Bark**

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S. asoca (Ashoka : N. O. Leguminosae) is well known for its medicinal properties. Its highly astringent stem bark is used in uterine affections in menorrhagia and scorpion sting¹. In the past, some chemical constituents have been reported to be present in this bark^{2,3,4}. The bark was extracted with acetone at room temperature and the concentrated viscous mass was subsequently macerated with petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol respectively.

The light petroleum extracted some waxy matter along with β -sitosterol. The ethylacetate extract on fractional precipitation with light petrol yielded a homogeneous compound (A). The acetone fraction on column chromatography on silica gel afforded compound (B), methanol fraction on repeated crystallisation with methanol-ethyl acetate yielded a homogeneous entity (C).

From a study of colour reactions, UV spectral data, acid hydrolysis, degradation, co-chromatography, mp, mmp compound (A) C₂₁H₂₄O₁₁ was identified as leucopelargonidin 3-O- β -D-glucoside by the well known procedure^{5,6}. Compound (B) C₁₅H₁₄O₆ was found to be identical with leucopelargonidin⁷ and compound (C) C₁₅H₁₄O₇ with leucocyanidin⁷.

The high astringency of the bark can be ascribed to the presence of these flavan-diols, and to the highly water soluble glycoside.

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**Studies on Heterocyclic Primary Amines. III :
Synthesis of N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)
Triphenyl Imidophosphoranes**

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IMIDOPHOSPHORANES in which the nitrogen atom is attached to heterocyclic ring are rare. Because of the increasing biological¹⁻⁶ and industrial⁷ uses of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives, we became interested in the preparation of new types of 1,3,4-oxadiazolylimidophosphoranes(I).

(I)

Ar

a = C₆H₅, b = *m*-ClC₆H₄, c = *p*-ClC₆H₄,
d = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄, e = *p*-CH₃OC₆H₄

The synthetic route which was found to be most convenient for the desired heterocyclic imidophosphoranes(I) employed the method of Horner and Oediger⁸. Thus, on subjecting 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole to dibromotriphenylphosphorane in dry benzene in the presence of triethylamine, at room temperature followed by four hours' reflux under nitrogen, the desired imidophosphoranes(I) were obtained in 70-80% yield.

The i.r. spectra of all the compounds(I) showed a band at about 1300 cm⁻¹ due to the N=P stretching vibration^{9a} with the concomitant disappearance of the NH stretching vibration at 3140 cm⁻¹ present in the starting aminooxadiazoles. The P-C (aromatic) stretching absorption was observed for all the compounds at 1440 cm⁻¹^{9b}. The i.r. spectra of all the compounds(I) also showed the cyclic C=N stretching bands at 1640-1690 cm⁻¹.